
Next-generation pediatric care: nanotechnology-based and AI-driven solutions for cardiovascular, respiratory, and gastrointestinal disorders

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Abstract

Background Global pediatric healthcare reveals significant morbidity and mortality rates linked to respiratory, cardiac, and gastrointestinal disorders in children and newborns, mostly due to the complexity of therapeutic management in pediatrics and neonatology, owing to the lack of suitable dosage forms for these patients, often rendering them “therapeutic orphans”. The development and application of pediatric drug formulations encounter numerous challenges, including physiological heterogeneity within age groups, limited profitability for the pharmaceutical industry, and ethical and clinical constraints. Many drugs are used unlicensed or off-label, posing a high risk of toxicity and reduced efficacy. Despite these circumstances, some regulatory changes are being performed, thus thrusting research innovation in this field.

Data sources Up-to-date peer-reviewed journal articles, books, government and institutional reports, data repositories and databases were used as main data sources.

Results Among the main strategies proposed to address the current pediatric care situation, nanotechnology is specially promising for pediatric respiratory diseases since they offer a non-invasive, versatile, tunable, site-specific drug release.

Tissue engineering is in the spotlight as strategy to address pediatric cardiac diseases, together with theragnostic systems. The integration of nanotechnology and theragnostic stands poised to refine and propel nanomedicine approaches, ushering in an era of innovative and personalized drug delivery for pediatric patients. Finally, the intersection of drug repurposing and artificial intelligence tools in pediatric healthcare holds great potential. This promises not only to enhance efficiency in drug development in general, but also in the pediatric field, hopefully boosting clinical trials for this population.

Conclusions Despite the long road ahead, the deepening of nanotechnology, the evolution of tissue engineering, and the combination of traditional techniques with artificial intelligence are the most recently reported strategies in the specific field of pediatric therapeutics.

Keywords Artificial intelligence · Conventional therapy · Nanotechnology · Pediatrics · Theragnostics

Introduction

Respiratory, cardiac, and gastrointestinal disorders pose a significant challenge to pediatric health worldwide. Epidemiological data indicated a considerable incidence of morbidity and mortality associated with these conditions, especially in prematurity [1–4]. Among the primary diseases in the field of pediatrics, conditions such as con-genital heart defects, asthma, pneumonia, chronic respiratory diseases, gastroesophageal reflux, peptic ulcers, and appendicitis, stand out. In the WHO European Region, lower respiratory tract infections were specifically identified as one of the leading causes of death for children aged 5–14 years [5].

However, the availability of specific medications for pediatrics and neonatology remains limited, both in the national and global contexts. Despite the progress made in recent years, the development and utilization of drugs in pediatrics are still associated with a wide variety of challenges. Pediatric patients encompass newborns, infants, children, and adolescents. These different age groups have distinct abilities to metabolize formulations, and their physiological and pharmacological characteristics differ significantly, making clinical trials in pediatrics more challenging than in adults [6].

Many unlicensed medications are provided to newborns and children in hospitals due to the lack of sufficient pedi-atric data to allow for appropriate dose adjustments. These adjustments are necessary not only because of lower body weight but also due to physiological differences within the pediatric population itself in relation to the adult popula-tion. In neonates, for example, the stomach does not produce Cytochrome P450 (CYP450) and its specific subfamilies, such as 1A2 and 2C9 (CYP1A2 and CYP2C9 respectively) represent some members of the cytochrome enzyme family involved in the metabolism of various substances, including drugs and other xenobiotics. gastric acid, the gastric emptying time is longer, pancreatic enzymes have low activity (Fig. 1), and there is a reduced release of bile acids and lipase. These factors can affect the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of drugs, making it necessary to increase or reduce the required dosage [7].

Fig. 1 Schematic representation of blood, body composition and physiological changes (stomach, liver, kidneys, heart, and lungs) according to age range (from premature/newborn to child/adolescent) (adapted from [7]). This figure was created using BioRender.

Many drugs, even those with licenses, are utilized off-label, meaning they are not used in accordance with license requirements [8]. Antiarrhythmics, antihypertensives, pro-ton-pump inhibitors, H₂-receptor antagonists, anti-asthmatic medications, and several antidepressants are frequently used off-label. This is not surprising, as two-thirds of medications used in pediatrics in the United States (US) are off-label. This percentage can be as high as up to three quarters globally [9]. A comparative study by Neuman et al. in 2018 [8] also showed that the number of prescriptions for unlicensed and off-label drugs in pediatric and neonatal units continues to increase in countries like Israel. Different forms of off-label use include drugs for unapproved indications, dosages or frequencies, routes of administration, or for unapproved populations (e.g., age groups). The majority of off-label prescriptions were due to patient age, meaning that the probability of receiving off-label treatment decreases as age increases [10]. The lack of suitable pediatric formulations necessitates the adaptation of available dosage forms through physical modification of drug products. This manipulation is usually necessary to adjust the drug product to the pediatric dose or to modify the final dosage form, particularly by transforming solid oral dosage forms into extemporaneously pre-prepared liquid formulations [11]. Nonetheless, ensuring dosing accuracy, evaluating depot formulations, and minimizing exposure to inappropriate excipients or amounts exceeding recommended intake can be challenging [12]. However, this approach carries risks as many of these medications have not been fully evaluated for their safety and efficacy specifically in pediatric patients. This can lead to complications and undesired side effects. A

recent study showed that only 14% of the off-label records for drugs launched in the Dutch Pediatric Formulary (DPF) dosing guidelines were supported by high-quality evidence, highlighting the risk for both toxicity and lack of efficacy [13].

Other reasons, such as insufficient evidence on drug molecules and safe excipients for these patients, a higher need to mask the taste of active pharmaceutical ingredients, difficulties in compounding management, low profitability, and clinical, regulatory, or ethical limitations, also unfavorably affect pediatric dosage form development [14, 15]. Significant progress has been made in the past 20 years in terms of regulatory aspects, particularly in the US (Pharmaceutic Research Equity Act and Best Pharmaceuticals for Children Act) and the EU (Pediatric Medicine Regulation) [16, 17].

Nevertheless, there are still some major shortcomings that need to be addressed during pediatric drug development, such as the segmentation of the pediatric population (i.e., adolescents vs. neonates) and drugs that target rare pediatric diseases, which is especially important when the disease greatly differs between adults and children. Despite these observed gaps, the aforementioned progress in legislation has spurred the development of specific and appropriate medications for the pediatric population [8, 18–22]. Considering the need for individualized targeting of the unique characteristics of pediatric and neonatal patients [23], whose ages vary widely, there is a huge demand for novel and effective medicines in this field.

Generally, pediatric drug development is often guided by advancements in adult drug development. This alignment poses no issues when the disease, such as asthma, affects both children and adults. Special attention should also be paid to diseases occurring exclusively in pediatric populations, such as pediatric brain cancer (pontine glioma). According to the maternal health policy and the head of pediatrics at Novartis, Dr. Christina Bucci-Rechtweg, when a disease occurs only in adults, “companies are exempted from the obligation to perform pediatric studies”, leading to “wasted opportunities for children with cancer because some of the adults drugs may be effective against certain child-hood cancers” [17]. That is, pediatric cancers are often distinct from those in adults. Since adult cancers do not appear in children, pharmaceutical companies can easily secure a waiver from the requirement to conduct pediatric studies. In other words, there is a lack of incentives for the development of rare pediatric diseases.

However, the scarcity of suitable medications for this age group and their regulatory limitations poses obstacles to meeting this demand. The development of innovative therapies is often challenging due to the complexity of developing biological systems and the ethical and safety constraints associated with clinical trials in children. This challenge is particularly acute in the case of newborns and premature infants, whose delicate health status demands specialized, tailored treatments. The fragility of their developing organs and immature immune systems further amplify the need for precise, age-appropriate pharmaceutical interventions. Additionally, the limited availability of research data and clinical evidence in this population contribute to the difficulty encountered in formulating effective and safe medications tailored to their specific needs.

Important regulatory aspects in the US and the Euro-pean Union are changing this scenario for the efficacy and safety accreditation in pediatrics. Clinical protocols of drugs developed for adults can be approved for pediatric use not only through clinical extrapolation but also through controlled trials when applicable in the pediatric population. The Pediatric Research Equity Act (PREA) of 2003, the Best Pharmaceuticals for Children Act (BPCA) of 2002, and the Pediatric Rule of 1998 contributed to a significant increase in pediatric studies submitted to the FDA. As required by the PREA of 2012, many clinical reviews of pediatric studies were conducted, and from 2012 to the present, around 500 products have been studied [24].

Various strategies have been explored, ranging from the use of conventional therapies to the utilization of more complex systems that can encompass nanotechnological systems. These systems include, among others, micellar, polymeric, lipidic, inorganic, dendritic, and magnetic platforms, which can be employed for drug delivery and diagnosis, such as theragnostic systems. This combined therapeutic approach offers the possibility of more precise and targeted administration, improved drug taste, minimization of side effects, and enhancement of treatment efficacy [15].

Furthermore, theragnostic systems have garnered significant interest, particularly for complex and heterogeneous diseases like neurological disorders and oncology [25]. Examples of theragnostic systems include nanoparticles capable of carrying therapeutic agents and imaging contrasts, providing a personalized and effective approach. This emerging technology holds promise for advancing the field of pediatrics, offering more targeted therapies while minimizing side effects.

Another innovative tool gaining attraction in the health-care field is artificial intelligence, emerging as a promising perspective for drug repurposing (DR) [26]. Through machine learning techniques and the analysis of large volumes of data, artificial intelligence can identify existing market-available substances that can be repurposed for the treatment of pediatric diseases. This DR approach has the potential to accelerate the development of new therapies, reduce costs, and mitigate associated risks [27].

Given these promising prospects, this review proves to be of utmost importance. It seeks to analyze recent advances in drug formulations for respiratory, cardiac, and gastrointestinal treatments for pediatric and neonatal patients, exploring conventional strategies as well as more complex ones like nanotechnology systems. Additionally, the application of theragnostic systems, combining diagnosis and therapy, will be addressed, providing an integrated and personalized approach to pediatric disease treatment. This critical analysis will enable the identification of knowledge gaps, offer insights for future research, and contribute to the development of more effective and safe therapeutic approaches for children and newborns.

Respiratory diseases

Conventional therapy

Healthcare practitioners are often compelled to utilize adult medications off-label or without a license when a pediatric formulation is not accessible. This practice can exceed 90% for newborns and babies, especially in pediatric intensive care units. Respiratory medicines have been evidenced as being more commonly prescribed inappropriately in pediatric patients in China [28]. Respiratory disorders are the major cause of hospital admission in both preterm and full-term neonates, wherein acute bronchitis and bronchiolitis are the most frequent causes. Sometimes, preterm infants were twice as likely to be (re)-hospitalized for respiratory diseases [29]. Off-label prescription of respiratory drugs is especially common in young children [30, 31], with anti-asthmatic agents being

among the most commonly employed off-label medicines in respiratory diseases [9]. Most off-label medications used for treating respiratory diseases in neonates and children are pre-scribed for conditions like asthma, accompanying chronic lung disease, and respiratory distress syndrome. Table 1 includes the main respiratory drugs used off-label in pediatric patients.

A study conducted between 2004 and 2008 analyzed the off-label use of respiratory drugs according to age and indication from a database of about two million children [35]. Inhaled bronchodilators and oral beta-2-agonists were the most frequently used drugs during the forecasted period. The bronchodilators were often used off-label to treat acute bronchitis or upper respiratory tract infections. The FDA exclusively recommends inhaled nitric oxide (INO) for infants with pulmonary hypertension associated with hypoxic respiratory failure. On the other hand, pediatric patients outside of the neonatal period frequently utilize INO off-label. Due to a lack of proof and healthcare expenditures associated with INO, inhaled prostacyclin is being used as an alternative.

In 2022, the European Medicines Agency (EMA) released 89 drugs for marketing authorization at their Annual Meeting, including Beyfortus. This is the first medication designed to protect newborns and infants throughout their first respiratory syncytial virus (RSV) season, a time of high community risk of RSV infection, from lower respiratory tract sickness caused by the virus. In addition, Evusheld, indicated for COVID-19 treatment in adults and adolescents from 12 years old, was also recommended. The expanded use of Adcirca was approved for treating pulmonary arterial hypertension (PAH) in pediatric patients aged two years and older [36].

Important regulatory changes in the US and the Euro-pean Union are addressing the evaluation of efficacy, safety, and pharmacokinetics in pediatric patients. Through both clinical extrapolations employing biomarkers and protocols applicable to the pediatric population, drugs initially developed for adults can be approved for pediatric use. Table 2 presents several studies on pediatric respiratory disorders conducted under the BPCA and PREA, based on sources from the FDA [24].

Table 1 Off-label medications applied in pediatric population divided by target organs or tissues. ACE stands for angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitor

Target organ or tissue	Drugs	Therapeutic group	Off-label reason	References
Respiratory tract	Salbutamol	Beta-2 adrenergic agonist	Indication, dose, and interval	[30, 32]
	Budesonide	Corticosteroid	Indication	[30, 32]
	Betamethasone	Corticosteroid	Age	[32]
	Beclomethasone	Corticosteroid	Indication	[30, 32]
	Ambroxol + Clenbuterol	Beta-2 adrenergic agonist	Indication	[30, 32]
	Ipratropium	Bronchodilator (anticholinergic drug)	Indication	[30, 33–35]
	Fluticasone	Corticosteroid	Indication, age, and dose	[30, 32, 34]
	Terbutaline	Beta-2 adrenergic agonist	Indication, age, and dose	[30]
	Cromolyn sodium	Antagonist of Protein S100-P	Age	[30]
	Fenoterol	Beta-2 adrenergic agonist	Indication and age	[30]
Cardiovascular tract	Furosemide	Diuretic	Indication, age, and dose	[33, 59, 60]
	Captopril	ACE	Dose	[59, 60]
	Spironolactone	Diuretic	Dose and age	[33, 59, 60]
	Propranolol	Beta adrenergic antagonist	Dose	[59, 60]
	Nitroprusside	Antihypertensive	Dose and age	[59]
	Enalapril	ACE	Dose	[59]
	Milrinone	Inotropic and vasodilatory properties	Age	[59, 60]
	Epinephrine	Adrenergic agent	Age	[33, 61]
	Dopamine	Adrenergic agent	Indication	[33, 59]
	Clonidine	Alpha-2 adrenergic agonist	Dose and age	[33, 61]
Gastrointestinal tract	Ranitidine	Histamine H2 receptor antagonist	Dosage, administration, and indication	[33]
	Ondansetron	Antiemetic	Indication and age	[33, 34, 71]
	Metoclopramide	Antiemetic	Indication and age	[33, 71,

				72
Nervous system	Pantoprazole	Proton-pump inhibitor	Indication	[33, 61]
	Morphine	Opioid	Age	[33, 61]
	Paracetamol	Analgesic and antipyretic	Age and dosage	[33, 61]
	Fentanyl	Analgesic	Age and indication	[33]
	Phenobarbital	Barbiturate	Dosage, dosing interval and indication	[73]
Systemic antibacterial	Midazolam	Benzodiazepine	Age	[33, 61]
	Gentamicin	Antibiotics	Dosage and dosing interval	[73]
	Amikacin	Antibiotics	Dosage, dosing interval and indication	[60]
	Benzylpenicillin	Antibiotics	Dosage	[73]
	Amoxicillin	Antibiotics	Dosing interval	[60]

Nanotechnology tools

Nanotechnology is a versatile and interdisciplinary field that revolutionizes disease treatment by offering solutions that minimize adverse effects, facilitate controlled and sustained release, and enable precise drug targeting. Nanoparticles can be effectively administered through diverse pharmaceutical routes, including oral, parenteral (injection), topical (application on the skin), nasal, and pulmonary [37].

Extensive research has focused on the development of nanocarriers for pulmonary application during the last decade (Fig. 2) [38]. This administration route provides rapid absorption, facilitated by the expansive surface area of the lungs (exceeding 100 m²) and the delicate epithelial layer that envelops the airways (with a thickness ranging from 0.2 to 1 μm), complemented by abundant vascularization [39]. Lungs exhibit relatively low enzymatic activity, contributing to sustained drug availability, and the non-invasive nature of pulmonary delivery promotes improved patient compliance with treatment regimens [40].

The pulmonary route of administration holds a crucial advantage in the treatment of respiratory ailments such as asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) [43], tuberculosis [44], and cystic fibrosis [45], as it facilitates the localized release of therapeutic agents, marking a significant advancement in respiratory disease treatment [46].

Table 2 Some pediatric studies of BPCA and PREA (FDA) from 2012 to present applied to respiratory tract [37]

Drugs (Trade Name)	Applicant	Pharmacology	Dosage form and regimen	Indication
Afatinib (GILOTRIF)	Boehringer Ingelheim Pharmaceuticals, Inc	ErbB family blocker	Tablets: 20 mg, 30 mg, 40 mg	ErbB deregulation metastatic non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) for children between 1 year to 60 mg (≥ 50 kg)
Aliskiren (Tekturna)	Noden Pharma DAC	Direct renin inhibitor	Oral pellets: 150 mg (20 to 50 kg) 150 a 300 mg (≥ 50 kg)	Hypertension in children from 6 y and weighting from 20 kg.
Atezolizumab (Tecentriq)	Genentech, Inc	Anti-PD-L1 monoclonal antibody	IV injection (15 mg/kg once every 21 days)	Unresectable or metastatic alveolar sarcoma to pediatric patients from 2 y of age
Azelastine hydrochloride/ fluticasone propionate (Dymista)	Meda Pharmaceuticals	Antihistamine/corticosteroid	Azelastine hydrochloride 0.1% and fluticasone propionate 0.037% nasal spray (1 spray per nostril twice daily)	Seasonal allergy for patients ≥ 6 y old
Ceftaroline fosamil (Teflaro®)	Cerexa, Inc., A Subsidiary of Forest Laboratories, LLC	Cephalosporin antibiotic	IV infusion	Community-acquired bacterial pneumonia (CABP) and bacterial skin and skin structure infections (ABSSSI) in children aged 2 mon to 18 y old

BPCA Best Pharmaceuticals for Children Act, PREA Pediatric Research Equity Act, ErbB epidermal growth factor receptor, IV intravenous infusion

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Fig. 2 Number of scientific publications recorded using the keywords “nanotechnology” AND “lung” OR “pulmonary” in Web of Science (WOS) Core Collection (last updated April 2024). No further refine-ments have been made

Large and/or hydrophilic molecules often face challenges in being efficiently absorbed through the nasal or pulmonary mucosa. Furthermore, direct administration of certain drugs into the respiratory tract can lead to local toxicity [41]. It is, therefore, instrumental to meticulously select appropriate pharmaceutical formulations and nanotechnological platforms to treat respiratory conditions. The optimal choice should consider factors such as the drug's properties, therapeutic effectiveness, the specific characteristics of the targeted disease, and the unique attributes of the administration route. Using nanocarriers via the pulmonary route offers a rapid onset of action and high bioavailability. Additionally, they bypass first-pass hepatic metabolism, minimize side effects, and reduce the required therapeutic dose due to their small size, ensuring delivery to the deepest airways.

Additionally, nanoparticles with a positive surface charge can effectively penetrate the lungs but may have toxic effects. To avoid toxicity, neutral or negatively charged nanoparticles are recommended. Coating nanoparticles with polyethylene glycol (PEGylation) enhances biocompatibility, prolongs circulation time, and reduces lung clearance by penetrating mucus and evading immune elimination. Alternatively, positively charged nanoparticles can improve uptake by alveolar macrophages, making them more suitable for treating lung infections. Coating approaches using pulmonary surfactant components or non-adhesive coatings like PEG or mucolytic agents overcome lung barriers, enhance drug delivery, and show promise in treating various lung conditions including COPD, pulmonary fibrosis, infections, allergies, and lung cancer [42].

The properties of nanoparticles can be achieved and fine-tuned through advanced technologies that enable the structural manipulation of diverse nanoparticle types, as well as the utilization of various materials in pharmaceutical formulations [38]. Currently, numerous nanopharmaceuticals for inhalation are in development [47–49]. Nanoparticles are a versatile option for lung drug delivery as they can be formulated into different pharmaceutical forms, such as nasal sprays, nebulizer solutions, or even smart devices, enabling controlled and targeted administration of the drug [50].

Polymeric nanoparticles may be composed of synthetic or natural polymers, and exhibit properties such as tunable size, controlled drug release, biocompatibility, and surface functionality, making them highly suitable for drug delivery. Polymeric nanoparticles are composed of polymer chains and can be designed to encapsulate drugs within a polymeric matrix, allowing for controlled release. Polymeric nanoparticles loaded with theophylline, a hydrophilic drug, and budesonide, a lipophilic drug, were co-encapsulated in poly(lactic acid) (PLA) nanoparticles using a double emulsification solvent diffusion method [51]. The nanoparticles exhibited spherical shapes with sizes ranging from 190 to 400 nm and zeta potentials of -10 to -16 mV. They demonstrated sustained drug release for 24 hours in simulated lung fluid, as well as permeability through airway epithelial cells. Cell viability remained unaffected after exposure to nebulized drug-loaded nanoparticles. Nebulization of the nanoparticles resulted in a high fine particle fraction for both theophylline and budesonide. These findings suggest that the PLA nanoparticles loaded with budesonide and theophylline are promising drug delivery systems for combination therapy in asthma and COPD.

Glutaraldehyde and PLGA were recently combined to develop a pulmonary drug delivery system to treat pediatric sepsis-induced acute lung injury. The fatality of this disease remains high, with the most common cause of mortality related to acute lung injury.

The co-polymeric nanoparticles developed in this study were loaded with ofloxacin and tacrolimus and showed promising results: prolonged drug release, non-inflammatory, and reported not hazardous for the body [52]. PLGA was also proposed to control the pulmonary release of actives like sildenafil, used to treat pulmonary arterial hypertension in children. In this case, the encapsulation of sildenafil "elicited more pulmonary specific and sustained vasodilation" in rats compared to other administration routes, suggesting a safer and more effective approach for pediatric patients [53].

Chitosan particles were recently proposed as a suspension for pediatric treatment of asthma. This condition is not only difficult to diagnose but also difficult to treat since most formulations for children are in liquid form, which can compromise the bioavailability of actives like Zafirlukast due to its low water solubility. Therefore, this study explored the possibility of loading Zafirlukast into chitosan nanoparticles with improved surface area for higher effectiveness. The total release of Zafirlukast was achieved within 30 minutes; the solubility of the active was improved, and the *in vivo* results were promising [54].

Nanoparticles made from lipid materials have also been widely explored for use in the respiratory tract. They can form highly stable and long-lasting drug delivery systems. Liposomes have been proposed as carriers of cationic peptides aiming to treat infections in cystic fibrosis patients, both adults and children [55].

One study was aimed to optimize the lipid nanoparticles to achieve the highest encapsulation efficiency and the best *in vitro* deposition profile for both adults and children [56]. More recently, researchers have aimed to develop a stable and effective mRNA pulmonary delivery system for treating various diseases, including genetic disorders. A library of lipid nanoparticle compositions was screened using a Design of Experiments (DOE) method in order to identify formulations with high potency both before and after aerosolization. The majority of formulations of lipid nanoparticles (LNPs) achieved encapsulation efficiencies exceeding 80%, maintaining stable physicochemical properties for up to 14 days of storage at 4 °C. The LNP formulations displayed larger particles and lower encapsulation efficiency upon nebulization. However, four leading formulations with improved *in vitro* capacity for intracellular protein expression, even after aerosolization, were identified and further evaluated *in vivo*.

These lead formulations demonstrated predominant expression of luciferase protein in the mouse lung, both before and after nebulization. This study highlights the potential of LNPs for aerosolization-mediated pulmonary delivery of mRNA therapeutics.

Another nanoparticle widely explored in respiratory administration is mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs). Their accumulation in the lungs makes them suitable for pulmonary drug delivery. They are easily functionalizable, possess a high surface area, have a substantial loading capacity, exhibit chemical inertness, and strong biocompatibility. MSNs can be equipped with "molecular gates" to trigger cargo release in response to external stimuli, making them ideal for controlled drug release. Gated MSNs have shown promising performance in improving drug bioavailability and have applications in sensing and communication between particles. Moreover, they have proven potential as adjuvants in vaccines like that against *Mycoplasma hyopneumoniae* [57]. Compared to conventional aerosols, MSNs allow for controlled on-demand drug release in the lungs. To generate inhaled formulations, MSNs are modified with lipid coatings or polymers to improve dispersibility. Nebulizers and dry powder inhalers are commonly used for aerosol generation, with nebulizers forming small droplets and spray drying being the preferred method for dry powders. This approach enhances the delivery of MSNs for inhalation and improves their suitability for pulmonary drug administration [42]. In summary, nanotechnology platforms present a diverse array of possibilities for respiratory tract treatment. By enabling precise drug targeting and delivery optimization, they hold significant promise as a therapeutic approach, especially in pediatric drug development. However, ongoing scientific progress is imperative to enhance the efficacy, safety, and feasibility of these platforms, paving the way for innovative and highly efficient therapies that can benefit patients with respiratory conditions.

Cardiac diseases

Conventional therapy

Congenital heart defects and heart failure are among the most important cardiac pathologies in pediatrics [58]. For diseases that affect the cardiovascular tract, there is a substantial use of off-label drugs in hospitals (Table 1).

Studies indicate that 76% to 78% of children with certain types of cardiovascular disease are prescribed at least one drug administered off-label during hospitalization. Most of these are drugs commonly used to treat hypertension in adults, such as furosemide, captopril, and spironolactone [58, 62], in addition to antiarrhythmic agents such as lidocaine and adrenergic agents, such as dopamine or epinephrine. Despite the numerous available molecules to treat cardiac diseases due to the high prevalence of this condition in adulthood, very few of these agents have been well studied in children, as evidenced by recent studies cited by the FDA [24] (Table 3).

Nanotechnology tools

Nanotechnology offers unique advantages in treating cardiac diseases. Nanoparticles can be tailor-made to deliver selected drugs to the site of action upon intravascular administration for tissue repair. Both angiogenesis and wound healing can be promoted using new nanomaterials. El-Sayed et al. [63] proposed the development of dopamine-chitosan-iron oxide nanocomposites for tissue repair that mimic mussel functions. These nanocomposites were produced by ionic gelation, and

results from *in vitro* scratch wound-healing studies confirmed their capacity to promote cell migration and wound closure, suggesting the potential use of such nanocomposites in vascular surgery.

The creation of a vascular graft for tissue engineering of tiny diameter arteries was reported by Kurobe et al. [64]. Female mice were surgically implanted with polylactic acid nanofibers, which had an inner luminal diameter of 0.5–0.6 mm, as *infra-renal* aortic interposition conduits. Survival of grafted animals was above 90% one year after implantation. Histological analysis showed the presence of F4/80-positive macrophages and CD31-positive endothelial monolayers, as well as smooth muscle cells. Within the same timeframe, the neo-extracellular matrix was found to consist mostly of collagen types I and III. Implanted mice showed a relevant increase in smooth muscle cell expression, as well as matrix metalloproteinases-2 and 9, and collagen types I and III. These findings confirm the potential use of these nanofibers for remodeling by autologous cells.

Other examples of nanomaterials for myocardial repair are carbon nanotubes. Li et al. [65] evaluated the effect of poly (N-isopropylacrylamide)-modified single-wall carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) to encapsulate cells and their potential use for myocardial repair. SWCNTs were incorporated into the polymeric hydrogel to develop an intramyocardial delivery system for brown adipose-derived stem cells (BASCs) in rats suffering from myocardial infarction, resulting in increased cell adhesion, proliferation, and engraftment of seeding cells. Zhou et al. [66] also confirmed that the cellular milieu provided by SWCNTs integrated into gelatin hydrogel scaffolds is suitable for cardiac tissue engineering *in vitro*, facilitating heart contraction and encouraging the production of electrochemically related proteins. When the scaffolds were implanted into infarcted hearts of rats, they were also able to inhibit the pathological deterioration of myocardium.

Sridharan et al. [67] developed polycaprolactone-gelatin nanofibrous scaffolds by electrospinning, which were then used to culture human-induced pluripotent stem cells (hPSC) to differentiate into functional cardiomyocytes. The authors noted a considerable increase in the expression of the cardiomyocyte markers MHC6 (Myosin Heavy Chain 6) and TNNT (Cardiac Troponin) genes in 2D cultures and the cardiac progenitor genes SIRPA (Signal Regulatory Protein Alpha) and ISL-1 (insulin gene enhancer protein 1) in 3D cultures, but no significant variations were seen in the appearance of the cells acquired in either type of culture. The 3D scaffolds were also shown to facilitate uniform cell migration and distribution, promoting the *in situ* differentiation of cardiomyocytes. This finding opens new perspectives on the use of such 3D nanofibrous scaffolds for cell differentiation for functional cardiomyocytes. The developed scaffolds are proposed as functional cardiac patches for myocardial repair [68].

Cardiac patches composed of methacrylated elastin and gelatin conjugated with carbon nanotubes (CNTs) were also proposed by Wang et al. [69]. They examined the effects of these patches on the repair of infarcted heart muscle in rats and minipigs. Four weeks after implanting cell-free patches or patches seeded with rat cardiomyocytes onto the heart, the authors reported effective tissue healing. In minipigs with infarcted hearts, similar results were observed following the implantation of cell-free patches or patches containing cardiomyocytes developed from hPSC.

Table 3 Some pediatric studies of BPCA and PREA (FDA) from 2012 to present applied to cardiometabolic and endocrine systems [24]

Drugs (Trade name)	Pharmacology	Dosage form and regimen	Indications
Dabigatran etexilate (Pradaxa®)	Anticoagulant	Capsule: 75–150 mg in pellets Sachets: 20–150 mg in pellets	Venous thromboembolism in pediatric patients up to 18 y old
Dulaglutide (Trulicity)	Glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP 1) receptor agonist	Injectable solution: 0.75 mg/0.5 mL or 1.5 mg/0.5 mL in a single dose pen	Supplement to glycemic control in individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus who are 10 y of age or older
Exenatide (Bydureon and Bydureon Beise)	Cardiometabolic and endocrine	Prolonged-release injectable suspension: 2 mg/0.65 mL	Supplement to diet and exercise to help juvenile patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus, aged 10 to 17, achieve glycemic control
Rivaroxaban (Xarelto®)	Anticoagulant	Granules: oral suspension 1 mg/mL Film-coated immediate-release tablets: 10–20 mg	Venous thromboembolism (VTE) and the decrease in the likelihood of recurrent VTE in pediatric patients under the age of eighteen years following the start of parenteral anticoagulant therapy for at least five days Thromboprophylaxis is administered to child patients with congenital heart disease (CHD) who have had the Fontan operation and are two years of age or older
Sacubitril/Valsartan (LCZ696) (Entresto)	Valsartan, angiotensin receptor blocker (ARB), sacubitril, and neprilysin inhibitor	Oral tablet Extemporaneous oral suspension	Patients aged one year to less than eighteen years old who suffer from pediatric heart failure with left ventricular systolic dysfunction

BPCA Best Pharmaceuticals for Children Act, PREA Pediatric Research Equity Act

Sun et al. [70] used antibody-conjugated superpara-magnetic iron oxide nanoparticles against the endothelial progenitor cell surface marker CD34 to load neutrophils as an approach to treating myocardial ischemic injury. The authors monitored the nanoparticles by magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) following their injection into the ischemic mouse heart, revealing their superior capacity for CD133(+) endothelial progenitor cell accumulation at the myocardial ischemic sites, in comparison to control mice. This strong targeting ability of neutrophils to the site of action promoted heart revascularisation and functional recovery.

Gastrointestinal diseases

Conventional therapy

Compared to the aforementioned groups of diseases, there is a lower prevalence of off-label drug use for diseases related to the gastrointestinal tract and others (Table 1). However, there is still a high occurrence of off-label prescriptions in these cases, with antiemetics and proton pump inhibitors being among the most frequently used types.

Gastrointestinal diseases in children are important triggers of public health since non-treated pathologies can lead to chronic inflammatory processes in adulthood [74]. Conditions such as gastritis, duodenitis, pancreatitis and others, should be taken into consideration. The research conducted by Zhaksylyk et al. [74] is one of the few studies shedding some light on the prevalence and epidemiology of gastro-intestinal diseases in the pediatric population. Moreover, in 2018, Scarpato et al. conducted a study on the prevalence of functional gastrointestinal disorders in children and adolescents across Europe [75].

The results showed considerable variations in the prevalence of these disorders among countries, with aerophagia, constipation, irritable bowel syndrome, and abdominal migraine being the most prevalent. Nevertheless, gastrointestinal disorders in children can significantly impact their development and growth, highlighting the importance of providing them with adequate and effective treatment (Table 4).

Nanotechnology tools

The treatment of gastrointestinal diseases with nanotechnology often aims to increase the bioavailability of drugs that are loaded into nanoparticles. Lipid nanoparticles have been suggested as an appropriate method for the oral administration of poorly water-soluble or insoluble medications since lipids are recognized as absorption enhancers [76]. Xing et al. [77] described the development of polyethylene glycol-polycaprolactone (PEG-PCL)-modified solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) for the loading of 2-methoxy-estradiol, which were then encapsulated into pH-sensitive microparticles. The authors reported that surface modification with hydrophilic polymers reduced particle size but did not compromise IC₅₀ (half maximal inhibitory concentration) in 4T1 cell lines. The anticancer drug was released from the microparticles following a controlled profile in the intestinal simulated media, and its release was pH sensitive. The drug's relative bioavailability increased by 140.86 times. SLNs offer significant advances for the oral administration of drugs. The lipids used in their composition act as absorption enhancers and they are known to combine their advantages with no toxicological risks [78]. Permana et al.

[79] described the development of SLNs surface-tailored with hydroxypropyl beta-cyclodextrin, incorporated into a gellan gum-based floating gel in situ system for the controlled release of two antioxidants (luteolin 7-O-beta-D-glucopyranoside and quercetin 7-O-beta-D-glucopyranoside). The authors reported a significant improvement in the stability of the SLNs in gastric media, together with the enhanced solubility of both compounds. Flow and floating properties were promoted by the incorporation of SLN into the gel, resulting in controlled release of the bioactives in fasted-state simulated gastric fluid. Under fed-state simulated gastric fluid, a sustained release pattern was recorded.

Another potential type of nanoparticles are those made from synthetic polymers, such as poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA) and poly-L-lactide (PLA) [80]. The synthesis of PLGA/PLA-PEG-FA nanoparticles loaded with 6-shogaol, an active ingredient in ginger, and their impact in a mouse model of colitis caused by dextran sulphate sodium were reported by Zhang et al. [81]. These nanoparticles showed effective stimulation of Raw 264.7 macrophage cells and facilitated receptor-mediated absorption by colon-26 cells. By controlling the expression of pro-inflammatory [interleukin (IL)-6, IL-1beta, tumor necrosis factor (TNF)-alpha, inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS)] and anti-inflammatory factors such as heme oxygenase-1 (HO-1) and nuclear factor E2-related factor (Nrf-2) factors, their oral administration significantly reduced colitis symptoms and accelerated the healing of colitis wounds.

Recently, a selenized polymer-lipid hybrid system was proposed by Ren et al. [82] for the oral delivery of tripterine for the treatment of enteritis. The nanoparticles exhibited a delayed release of the payload and improved stability in gastrointestinal fluids compared to the non-selenized nanoparticles. A high cellular uptake in Caco-2 cells was also recorded, together with an oral bioavailability enhancement of 397% (selenized) and 280% (non-selenized) compared to the free drug suspension. The *in vivo* anti-enteritis activity was confirmed, fostering the relevance of such type of nanoparticles for the treatment of ulcerative colitis. The presence of selenium further strengthened the *in vivo* anti-inflammatory efficacy of the formulation.

An important concern that needs to be considered is the nanoparticle consumption through diet and foodstuff. Diao et al. [83] raised the concern about the use of silicon dioxide nanoparticles as additives in the food industry and their potential health risks in children. The authors evaluated the effects of orally administered silicon dioxide nanoparticles in young mice gut microbiota over 28 days. While they did not trigger intestinal or neuronal inflammation, there was a significant impairment in spatial learning and memory and locomotor inhibition in the mice, showing a remarkable damage in the tissue integrity. The study also revealed an unexpected increase in microbial diversity in the nanoparticle-treated mice. The

authors raised the hypothesis that neurobehavioral impairments and brain damage induced by the nanoparticles can be associated to the disruption of gut–brain axis caused by gut substances such as Vipr1 (vaso-active intestinal peptide receptor 1) and Sstr2 (somatostatin receptor). This highlights the risk of neurotoxicity of such particles in the pediatric population.

Another type of nanoparticle commonly found in food-stuff is food grade titanium dioxide nanoparticles. Gao et al. [84] studied the influence of such particles on nutrient absorption and metabolism in rats. The authors reported that both titanium dioxide micro and nanoparticles induced inflammatory infiltration in small intestine, causing flat apical membranes with sparse microvilli. Nanoparticles were more easily absorbed, reaching systemic circulation and resulting in changes in amino acids serum levels. The findings of this study suggest the need to monitor the levels of food containing such particles, particularly for children and the elderly, who need a high protein diet, as well as for people suffering from intestinal inflammation or metabolic disease.

Synthetic zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles have also been extensively used in livestock production. Zhu et al. [85] studied their effects on the gut microbiota in rats using 16S ribosomal RNA (rRNA). ZnO nanoparticles obtained through high-temperature thermal decomposition exhibited low cytotoxicity while demonstrating high antibacterial activity. In addition, these nanoparticles can also enhance probiotics, such as lactobacillus, and provide the antipathogenic effects.

Theragnostic systems: advances in pediatrics and neonatology

Theragnostics is a multidisciplinary field that combines therapy and diagnosis, leveraging the advantages of nanoscale particles (Fig. 3). This approach enables the development of nanosensors and nanomedicine, leading to significant advancements in the realm of diagnosis and treatment. Nanotheragnostic-based therapy, in turn, aims to apply and refine nanomedicine strategies to achieve advanced theragnostics [86]. This involves the use of various nanocarriers, such as polymeric conjugates, metallic and inorganic nano-particles like gold [87] and silica nanoparticles, dendrimers [88], micelles [89], liposomes [90], carbon nanotubes [91], and biodegradable polymer nanoparticles [92]. These carriers allow for controlled, targeted, and sustained delivery of diagnostic and therapeutic agents, resulting in more effective theragnostic effects with fewer undesirable side effects. Additionally, nanotechnological intervention also facilitates disease prognosis, diagnosis, and related therapeutic strategies through a common platform.

Furthermore, nanotheragnostic systems, by utilizing nanomaterials with distinctive optical and personalized properties, can be tailored to perform multifunctional roles as demonstrated with gold nanoparticles [87]. The use of pegylated nanocarriers is also noteworthy, as they exhibit low immunogenicity and antigenicity, thereby increasing residence time and stability in the organism [93, 94].

Nanotheragnostic systems often require imaging equipment such as ultrasound, MRI, positron emission tomography (PET)/computed tomography (CT) imaging, and optimization of imaging sequences such as optical imaging (fluorescence and bioluminescence imaging) to monitor targeted drug and gene delivery [93]. This is because the nanomaterials used have the ability to detect and display areas of serious health concerns. These contributions drive innovation and advance medicine towards more effective and personalized therapies [95]. Recent studies have emphasized the importance of nanoparticulate systems as emerging technologies in ultrasound-based theragnostics [96].

Fig. 3 Schematic representation of nanotheranostic systems to be used for both diagnostic and therapeutic purposes as a single platform. This figure was created using BioRender

There are advantages and disadvantages associated with the different contrast agents frequently studied for theragnostics [97, 98]. The main advantages identified in these studies include: (1) the integration of contrast agents, that are generally small molecules, into theragnostic nanoparticles can overcome many of the problems associated with administering these agents alone; (2) drug-carrying nanoparticles can have contrast agents conjugated or encapsulated on their surface to provide non-invasive early diagnostics and real-time treatment monitoring; (3) nanoparticles with strong optical absorption, such as gold nanocages, can be used as contrast agents for photoacoustic imaging; (4) quantum dots (QDs) are excellent imaging probes because of their great photosensitivity and easily adjustable fluorescence wavelength; and (5) for MRI, Mn-based contrast agents can be utilized as T1 contrast agents. Their sustained release is pH-sensitive, and their imaging performance is comparable to that of commercial Gd-based contrast agents. Regarding the disadvantages, the authors noted: (1) QDs have limited use in biological systems due to their toxicity and non-biodegradability; (2) metallic oxide nanoparticles can cause chronic inflammation and toxicity in chronic airway diseases; (3) nanoparticles must be able to cross cell membranes to exert a therapeutic effect, but the lipophilic cell membrane hinders the entry of large, charged molecules, except by endocytosis, and (4) the quantity of therapeutic drug or nanoparticle that can reach the cytoplasm is limited when it comes to endocytosis-induced nanoparticles that are trapped in the endosomes; these endosomes then fuse with lysosomes for particle breakdown [99]. There are numerous ongoing studies regarding the potential use of theragnostic systems for the treatment of neoplastic diseases. However, Poot et al. [100] described the current state of theragnostics in adult oncology and the limited use of theragnostics in pediatric oncology. This may be applicable to other pathologies such as respiratory, cardiac, and gas-tric diseases. While theragnostics

has demonstrated its worth in adult oncology, its application in pediatric cancer has received limited attention and is still in its infancy [100]. The studies found are especially related to the central nervous system in children. For example, in a cohort study among the theragnostics tested, SSTR2a and CXCR-4 (alpha-chemokine receptor specific for stromal-derived-factor-1) emerged as promising antigens for pediatrics medulloblastoma. In addition, CXCR-4 evidenced potential for atypical teratoid rhabdoid tumors and ependymoma. B7-H3 (a type I membrane protein also known as CD276, that costimulate or downmodulate T-cell responses) also showed promise as a target for pediatric theragnostics in the nervous system due to its high expression at both RNA and protein levels [101]. Another study by Niessen et al. revealed the use of biologicals as a promising approach, such as antibody-fragments, for radionuclide therapy and nuclear imaging in pediatric oncology [102].

In chronic lung disorders, anatomical and biological limitations make it difficult to administer drugs and contrast agents effectively. Given this, research is increasingly focused on how nanoparticle technology can overcome these obstacles and improve the identification and management of long-term respiratory conditions. Special attention has been given to the recent development of multifunctional theragnostic nanoparticles that integrate therapeutic and imaging capabilities. In this context, the challenges that must be addressed before these nanoparticles can be clinically applied are emphasized, such as evaluating their long-term toxicity, particle accumulation, degradation, and elimination, as well as the correlation between their in vivo behaviors and physicochemical properties. Furthermore, studies have demonstrated the use of nanoparticles for imaging in chronic respiratory diseases and respective drug delivery [103]. This research contributes to advancing knowledge and developing innovative therapeutic strategies in the field of chronic respiratory diseases [104–108].

Advances in the intratracheal delivery of hyperpolarized gases and nano- and microparticles for imaging and treating respiratory illnesses were reported by Wang et al. [109]. The authors argue that precise theragnostics for respiratory disorders can benefit greatly from intratracheal administration of nanoparticles in imaging. Additionally, they emphasized how the unique structure of the lungs provides a means of delivering particles straight into the lungs without causing harm. This allows for better targeted molecular imaging, increased lung accumulation, and enhanced treatment efficacy. Another advantage of using the pulmonary route for nanoparticles is their versatility, which favors precision imaging and therapy at the molecular level. This leads to innovative and non-invasive approaches to precisely diagnose and treat respiratory diseases [109]. Intratracheal delivery strategies benefit from this versatility as different colors correspond to different sizes of particles being delivered via the airways and how they settle in the lungs. When administered intratracheally, multifunctional nanoparticles are directly deposited in the lungs. This enables accurate multi-modal imaging, such as PET, MR, and optical imaging, and respiratory illness therapy. Figure 4 illustrates the pathway of multifunctional nanoparticles upon intratracheal administration being deposited in the lungs for precise multimodal imaging and therapy of respiratory disease.

Suer and Bayram [110], discussed the possible theragnostic applications of liposomes as nanocarriers in chronic inflammatory lung disorders (CILDs), like asthma and COPD. In addition to evaluating current treatments for CILDs, the authors highlighted the need for new effective therapeutics. Among the addressed nanoparticles, liposomes were emphasized. These lipid-based nanoparticles, capable of carrying drugs and imaging agents, enabling simultaneous therapy and diagnosis, may be a suitable option for a novel form of therapy in CILD treatment. The types of liposomes and their potential for drug delivery to specific cells in the lungs were also addressed [110].

The use of ultrasound-based systems in cardiovascular medicine, especially pediatric cardiology, is interesting with regard to the application of theragnostic agents in cardiac treatments. In fact, recent clinical trials for theragnostics in cardiac diseases, based on ultrasound, have recently been reviewed [111]. The authors point out that one important benefit of

using contemporary ultrasound systems is their portability. Targeted therapies might be used as therapeutic devices at the point of care, which would boost effective-ness and shorten recovery times. In a pediatric context, this might be especially pertinent. Therefore, with the effective, focused, and non-invasive application of recently developed technology, customized medicine in contemporary clinical practice may soon become a reality.

High-frequency ultrasound is used in sonothrombolysis, a therapeutic procedure, to break up clots in pediatric patients. This technique has potential applications in the cardiovascular domain, including the treatment of childhood venous thromboembolism (VTE), catheter-induced vasospasm, and arteriovenous shunt management. This approach proves to be a safe alternative for the treatment of pediatric VTE, especially in cases involving central venous catheters, where current treatments present significant risks [112]. Additionally, Jani et al. [111] demonstrated that ultrasound-induced microbubble cavitation showed promising results in resolving vasospasm and restoring distal arterial flow after peripheral artery injuries. This could potentially be explored as a treatment for catheter-induced vasospasm in infants and congenital heart disease in children. In the context of con-genital heart diseases, image-guided sonothrombolysis also shows potential for therapies in palliative shunts, reducing thrombotic burden in arteriovenous shunts and presenting success in the treatment of pulmonary thromboembolism. These applications highlight the promising clinical impact of sonothrombolysis in the treatment of pediatric thrombo-embolic diseases [112].

In another study, Spivak and co-workers demonstrated the potential of gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) for biomedical applications, particularly in the treatment of heart failure. The study suggests that AuNPs can be used for drug delivery and have cardioprotective effects in rats with doxorubicin-induced heart failure, superior to that of Simdax. The study also suggests that intrapleural (local) administration is preferable to intravenous (systemic) according to all parameters tested. The sonoporation effect was tested to enhance the delivery of nanoparticles into myocardial cells, which may have implications for the development of innovative drug delivery strategies. The promising outcomes of this study showcased the potential of AuNPs in the fields of nanocardiology, nanoendocrinology, and nanoneurology for the creation of cutting-edge treatments as well as novel drug delivery personalization and stratification [113].

Fig. 4 When administered intratracheally, multifunctional nanoparticles are deposited directly in the lungs, enabling accurate multimodal imaging (such as PET, MR, and optical imaging) and respiratory illness treatment. This figure was created using BioRender

Artificial intelligence as a promising tool for drug repurposing

DR, often referred to as repositioning, redirecting, or repro-filing, is a desirable and financially feasible tactic for discovering novel applications for authorized or in-development pharmaceuticals that deviate from their intended therapeutic indication [114, 115]. The main advantages of this approach include a lower risk of failure, a reduced time frame, and less investment needed [114, 116]. The costs involved in drug design and development are estimated to be between \$2 and \$3 billion, whereas repurposing a drug to the market has been estimated to cost an average of \$300 million. The total development time for new drugs takes at least 13 to 15 years [117, 118]. Theoretically, DR is a faster process, since some of the early stages of drug development are already done and completed. Therefore, a recent systematic review points out that this fact is unclear due to conflicting evidence on this matter [119]. In any case, considering that DR avoids phase I clinical trials if the safety profile is already well-established, and that the molecules have already been previously authorized for other purposes (which could speed regulatory review and approval), DR could take 3–12 years.

This tool is particularly relevant in pediatric population since therapeutic gaps in such population often result in off-label use of drugs otherwise new uses are studied of already existing medicines. It is, therefore, instrumental to retrieve evidence-based information in this field to ensure the safe use of drugs in children.

A DR strategy typically comprises of three steps: finding a potential molecule for a certain indication (hypothesis); evaluating the drug's efficacy in preclinical animals mechanistically; and phase II clinical trial efficacy evaluation [116].

Nevertheless, there are factors that contribute to failure in the repurposing industry, including organizational barriers, regulatory concerns, and patent considerations [116]. Additionally, potential medications may be shelved because of low market potential, industry consolidation, inadequate efficacy, or superiority over alternative therapies. The main obstacles to realizing the full potential of repurposing as a fundamental strategy in drug development include insufficient funding, data access issues, and difficulties negotiating intellectual property. The main enablers are multi-partner collaborations, the availability and use of compound data-bases, and tax incentives [119].

Therefore, independent clinical trials headed by academic institutions, research centers, or cooperative groups are the main means by which DR research is carried out [120]. Social network analysis (SNA) techniques are used to analyze scientific collaboration networks in order to identify leaders based on the strength of their contacts within research networks, with the goal of exchanging knowledge and skills to expedite DR [121].

Recent studies illustrate the benefits of DR: repurposing antidiabetic drugs has shown potential for cardiovascular disease [122]; a multi-target and multi-objective model has identified drugs with potential application in the treatment of preeclampsia [123]; temipenem pivoxil has been found to be a potent therapy for severe diarrhea caused by multi-drug resistant *Shigella* [124]; repurposing clinically approved medications against vaccinia and variola viruses will likely be effective against monkey pox virus (MPXV) [125]; the use of DR in the discovery of a treatment for hand, foot and mouth disease (HFMD) shows that existing antiviral drugs could be effective treatments [126]; and there is more potential to investigate the oxazolidinone, fluoroquinolone, and nitroimidazole classes of chemicals for the development of tuberculosis drugs [127].

DR is performed either experimentally or computationally (also called *in silico* DR), which is part of computational pharmacology [128]. *Silico* DR falls into two categories: identifying novel uses for already approved medications (drug-centric) and finding potent medications for a sickness (disease-centric). Both approaches share the similarity evaluation method between medications and/or illnesses [129].

Drug–target interaction (DTI) describes how a drug (a chemical substance) binds to a target (such as proteins or nucleic acids), altering its biological behavior or function. This is an important strategy for drug repurposing [130, 131], as it can expedite and lower the necessary expenditures of drug development. DTI prediction is a crucial component of this process. In an effort to speed up drug development and reduce time to market, researchers have therefore increased their efforts to determine the interaction between medications and targets [132].

A new set of candidate molecules is systematically suggested by DTI predictions made *in silico*, which speeds up the drug–target (DT) process by addressing the information between molecules and successfully estimating the interaction strength of new DT pairs based on prior DT trials [133–135]. The literature describes four categories of *in silico* DTI prediction techniques: network-based, molecular docking, similarity-based, and deep learning-based models [135, 136]. A simulation-based method called “molecular docking” uses the characteristics of molecules (ligands) and proteins (receptors) [135, 137]. Network-based techniques are derived from link prediction algorithms found in complex networks and algorithms utilized in recommender systems [136].

Experiments may be guided, latent patterns in massive drug or protein data collections can be found, and hitherto unheard-of knowledge can be extracted from drug–target networks using deep learning-based techniques [138]. To compute feature descriptors, or fingerprints, for the drug–target pair, most methods rely on features. These fingerprints are then used to train a machine learning prediction model [131]. Some of these techniques include:

(1) deep learning stacked auto-encoders [132]; (2) convolutional neural networks (CNN) [139]; (3) molecular graph convolution (MGC) [140]; (4) ensembles of multi-output bi-clustering trees (eBICT) [138]; (5) network-based inference (NBI) techniques derived from recommendation algorithms [136]; (6) combining multiple kernels into a tripartite heterogeneous drug–target–disease interaction space to integrate multiple biological sources simultaneously [141]; and (7) graph neural network models [134]. Molecule input embedding was accomplished using a modified BERT transformer [135], and a semi-supervised model for molecule embedding called SMILES-BERT was proposed using a BERT transformer [142]. Word2vec [143] was used to represent the embedding of genes [144]. Using graph neural networks (GNNs) and Bi-LSTM [145], a graph and sequence fusion learning model was proposed to extract meaningful information from a chemical graph and a SMILES sequence [146].

In the DTI prediction task, feature descriptors are essential since the inputs must be transferred to a different representation for the machine learning model to function [147, 148]. As an illustrative example, one-hot encoding [132, 149, 150], character embedding [135, 139, 141], and graphs [134, 136, 138] are some of the approaches already used, together with Extended Connectivity Fingerprints (ECFP) and Protein Sequence Composition (PSC) for molecules and proteins representation, respectively [140]. Custom molecule representations, where each sequence symbol is considered a time point, have also been reported [151]. A deep neural network, like CNN, has layers organized to specify the architecture of the model, which, when used for a DTI task, automatically extracts features from input data, reflects knowledge, and yields the required output [135, 139] (Fig. 5). The DTI prediction model from (148) is composed of three steps: input, representation, and the machine learning model. In the input stage, the molecule (drug) is represented in SMILES and the protein (target) is represented by its sequence of amino acids. In the representation stage, using a MER-based

approach, the inputs are represented by images, creating a visual signature for both molecule and protein. Lastly, the machine learning model is employed, which is a two-head neural network, with one CNN for the molecule and another CNN for the protein. These are concatenated together as a vectorized input to a fully connected neural network, whose output is the predicted binding affinity between the molecule and the protein.

Fig. 5 The deep learning DTI general strategy. The inputs consist of protein and molecule sequences (SMILES) mapped to a new representation. The new representation for the molecules and proteins is fed into two CNN-based deep neural networks, which concatenate and feed into a dense, fully connected network whose output is the DTI prediction. *DTI* drug-target interaction, *CNN* convolutional neural network.

The validation of drug repurposing outcomes can be achieved by comparing predicted targets in PubMed, Clinical Trials, or electronic health records (EHRs), which were utilized to validate the metformin effects associated with cancer mortality [128]. Other methods of validation include area under the receiver-operating characteristics (AUROC) values as well as specificity, sensitivity, positive predictive value (PPV) [152], precision–recall curve (PRC) [153], and area under the PRC (AUPRC) [154]. Experimental validation of drugs requires animal studies and cell-based targeted tests, both in vitro and in vivo [155].

Technological developments in sequencing have enabled the collection of vast amounts of detailed genomic data from numerous individuals, which may be valuable for the repurposing of drugs [115]. However, the challenges in this field involve the difficulties in handling large amount of data. For instance, Illumina's HiSeq X Ten machine can sequence over 18,000 complete human genomes annually, producing 3.6 petabytes of data [156]. Despite promising advances in the field of DR, more research is required to determine how best to support it with resources, particularly financial ones, staffing for out-licensing shelved products, and legal knowledge to negotiate intellectual property agreements in multi-partner collaborations [121].

Conclusions

In conclusion, while there exists substantial global concern over reducing infant mortality rates, it is evident that further efforts are required to enhance the effectiveness and safety of pediatric therapies. Despite the complexity of

personalizing treatments for these young patients, notable progress has been achieved in recent years. The widespread unlicensed or off-label use of adult-developed drugs, particularly in neonatal intensive care units, under-scores the pressing need for tailored pediatric solutions. Moreover, investigations into off-label prescriptions in pediatrics, focusing on adjustments for indication, age, and dosage have shed light on common practices. Respiratory medications, notably adrenergic agonists, and corticosteroid drugs, emerge as the most frequently pre-scribed off-label treatments, particularly for asthma and chronic lung disease. In FDA clinical trials, personalized dosage forms for infants with respiratory, cardiac, and gastrointestinal conditions predominantly take oral forms, including pellets, chewable tablets, film-coated immediate-release tablets, sachets, capsules, and extemporaneous oral suspensions. Notably, alternative formulations such as nasal sprays, injectables, and lyophilized powders for reconstitution for intravenous infusion have also been developed, extending treatment options available for a range of pediatric conditions. Furthermore, nanotechnological advancements offer a diverse array of possibilities for addressing respiratory, cardiac, and gastrointestinal tract conditions. Precision drug targeting and optimized delivery methods are at the forefront of pediatric drug development strategies. The integration of nanotechnology and theragnostics stands poised to refine and propel nanomedicine approaches, ushering in an era of innovative and personalized drug delivery for pediatric patients. Finally, the promising intersection of drug repurposing and artificial intelligence tools in pediatric healthcare holds great potential. This promises not only to enhance efficiency but also to revolutionize the in-silico design of new drugs, drawing on comprehensive institutional databases while conscientiously considering ethical and physiological considerations.

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Declarations

Conflict of interest No financial or non-financial benefits have been received or will be received from any party related directly or indirectly to the subject of this article.

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References

1. WHO. Child mortality and causes of death. 2023. Available from: <https://www.who.int/data/gho/data/themes/topics/topic-details/GHO/child-mortality-and-causes-of-death>. Accessed 30 Oct 2023.
2. França EB, Lansky S, Rego MAS, Malta DC, França JS, Teix-eira R, et al. Principais causas da mortalidade na infância no Brasil, em 1990 e 2015: estimativas do estudo de Carga Global de Doença. *Rev Bras Epidemiol.* 2017;20:46–60.
3. Divecha C, Tullu MS, Chaudhary S. Burden of respiratory ill-nesses in pediatric intensive care unit and predictors of mortality: experience from a low resource country. *Pediatr Pulmonol.* 2019;54:1234–41.
4. Attard TM, Miller M, Pant C, Kumar A, Thomson M. Mortality associated with gastrointestinal bleeding in children: a retrospective cohort study. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2017;23:1608.
5. Kyu HH, Stein CE, Boschi Pinto C, Rakovac I, Weber MW, Dannemann Purnat T, et al. Causes of death among children aged 5–14 years in the WHO European Region: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2016. *Lancet Child Adolesc Heal.* 2018;2:321–37.
6. Lam JKW, Xu Y, Worsley A, Wong ICK. Oral transmucosal drug delivery for pediatric use. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev.* 2014;73:50–62.
7. Yellepeddi VK, Joseph A, Nance E. Pharmacokinetics of nano-technology-based formulations in pediatric populations. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev.* 2019;151–152:44–55.
8. Nir-Neuman H, Abu-Kishk I, Toledano M, Heyman E, Ziv-Baran T, Berkovitch M. Unlicensed and off-label medication use in pediatric and neonatal intensive care units: no change over a decade. *Adv Ther.* 2018;35:1122–32.
9. Ivanovska V, Rademaker CMA, Van Dijk L, Mantel-Teeuwisse AK. Pediatric drug formulations: review of challenges and progress. *Pediatrics.* 2014;134:361–72.
10. Allen HC, Garbe MC, Lees J, Aziz N, Chaaban H, Miller JL, et al. Off-label medication use in children, more common than we think: a systematic review of the literature. *J Okla State Med Assoc.* 2018;111:776.
11. Kasahun AE, Sendekie AK. Are pediatrics taking the prescribed tablet dosage form? Practices of off-label tablet modification in pediatric wards: a prospective observational study. *Heliyon.* 2023;9:e15109.
12. Rautamo M, Kvarnström K, Sivén M, Airaksinen M, Lahdenne P, Sandler N. A focus group study about oral drug administration practices at hospital wards—aspects to consider in drug development of age-appropriate formulations for children. *Pharmaceutics.* 2020;12:1–13.
13. van der Zanden TM, Smeets NJL, de Hoop-Sommen M, Schw-erzel MFT, Huang HJ, Barten LJC, et al. Off-label, but on-evidence? a review of the level of evidence for pediatric pharmacotherapy. *Clin Pharmacol Ther.*

14. Galande AD, Khurana NA, Mutalik S. Pediatric dosage forms - challenges and recent developments: a critical review. *J Appl Pharm Sci.* 2020;10:155–66.
15. Marques MS, Lima LA, Poletto F, Contri RV, Kulkamp Guerreiro IC. Nanotechnology for the treatment of paediatric diseases: a review. *J Drug Deliv Sci Technol.* 2022;75: 103628.
16. Guidi B, Parziale A, Nocco L, Maiese A, La Russa R, Di Paolo M, et al. Regulating pediatric off-label uses of medicines in the EU and USA: challenges and potential solutions: Comparative regulation framework of off label prescriptions in pediatrics: a review. *Int J Clin Pharm.* 2022;44:264–9.
17. Spadoni C. Pediatric drug development: challenges and opportunities. *Curr Ther Res.* 2019;90:119–22.
18. Asfour MH, Abd El-Alim SH, Kassem AA, Salama A, Gouda AS, Nazim WS, et al. Vitamin D3-loaded nanoemulsions as a potential drug delivery system for autistic children: formulation development, safety, and pharmacokinetic studies. *AAPS Pharm-SciTech.* 2023;24:58.
19. Been S, Choi J, Lee YH, Kim PY, Kim WK, Cho HH, et al. Improvement of medication adherence and controlled drug release by optimized acetaminophen formulation. *Macromol Res.* 2021;29:342–50.
20. Kean EA, Adeleke OA. Orally disintegrating drug carriers for paediatric pharmacotherapy. *Eur J Pharm Sci.* 2023;182:106377.
21. Yoo O, Tang EKY, Salman S, Nguyen MN, Sommerfield D, Sommerfield A, et al. A randomised controlled trial of a novel tramadol chewable tablet: pharmacokinetics and tolerability in children. *Anaesthesia.* 2022;77:438–48.
22. Laquintana V, Asim MH, Lopodota A, Cutrignelli A, Lopalco A, Franco M, et al. Thiolated hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin as mucoadhesive excipient for oral delivery of budesonide in liquid paediatric formulation. *Int J Pharm.* 2019;572:118820.
23. Cirri M, Maestrini L, Maestrelli F, Mennini N, Mura P, Ghelar-dini C, et al. Design, characterization and in vivo evaluation of nanostructured lipid carriers (NLC) as a new drug delivery system for hydrochlorothiazide oral administration in pediatric therapy. *Drug Deliv.* 2018;25:1910–21.
24. FDA. Reviews of pediatric studies conducted under BPCA and PREA from 2012–present. 2023. Available: <https://www.fda.gov/drugs/development-resources/reviews-pediatric-studies-conducted-under-bpca-and-prea-2012-present>. Accessed 30 Oct 2023.
25. The Business Research Company. Theranostics Market Size, Trends, Growth | 2024 to 2033. 2024. Available: <https://www.thebusinessresearchcompany.com/report/theranostics-global-market-report>. Accessed 8 July 2024.
26. May M. Eight ways machine learning is assisting medicine. *Nat Med.* 2021;27:2–3.
27. Matsushita FY, Krebs VLJ, de Carvalho WB. Artificial intelligence and machine learning in pediatrics and neonatology healthcare. *Rev Assoc Med Bras.* 2022;68:745–50.
28. Cui J, Zhao L, Liu X, Liu M, Zhong L. Analysis of the potential inappropriate use of medications in pediatric outpatients in China. *BMC Health Serv Res.* 2021;21:1–12.
29. Houweling LMA, Bezemer ID, Penning-Van Beest FJA, Meijer WM, Van Lingen RA, Herings RMC. First year of life medication use and hospital admission rates: premature compared with term infants. *J Pediatr.* 2013;163:61–6.e1.
30. Schmiedel S, Fischer R, Ibanez L, Fortuny J, Klungel OH, Reynolds R, et al. Utilisation and off-label prescriptions of

-
- respiratory drugs in children. *PLoS ONE*. 2014;9:e105110.
31. Conroy S, McIntyre J, Choonara I. Unlicensed and off label drug use in neonates. *Arch Dis Child Fetal Neonatal Ed*. 1999;80:142–5.
 32. Jong GW, Eland IA, Sturkenboom MCJM, van den Anker JN, Stricker BHC. Unlicensed and off-label prescription of respiratory drugs to children. *Euro Respir J*. 2004;23:310–3.
 33. Shah SS, Hall M, Goodman DM, Feuer P, Sharma V, Fargason C, et al. Off-label drug use in hospitalized children. *Arch Pediatr Adolesc Med*. 2007;161:282–90.
 34. Yackey K, Stukus K, Cohen D, Kline D, Zhao S, Stanley R. Off-label medication prescribing patterns in pediatrics: an update. *Hosp Pediatr*. 2019;9:186–93.
 35. Kuch BA, Saville AL, De Toledo JS, Venkataraman ST. Inhaled pulmonary vasodilators: are there indications within the pediatric ICU? *Respir Care*. 2017;62:678–98.
 36. Agency EM. ANNUAL REPORT 2022. 2022. Available: <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/annual-report/2022/index.html> Accessed 8 July 2024.
 37. Chenthamara D, Subramaniam S, Ramakrishnan SG, Krish-naswamy S, Essa MM, Lin FH, et al. Therapeutic efficacy of nanoparticles and routes of administration. *Biomater Res*. 2019;23:1–29.
 38. Pontes JF, Grenha A. Multifunctional nanocarriers for lung drug delivery. *Nanomaterials*. 2020;10:183.
 39. Qin L, Cui Z, Wu Y, Wang H, Zhang X, Guan J, et al. Challenges and strategies to enhance the systemic absorption of inhaled peptides and proteins. *Pharm Res*. 2023;40:1037–55.
 40. Labiris NR, Dolovich MB. Pulmonary drug delivery. Part I: physiological factors affecting therapeutic effectiveness of aerosolized medications. *Br J Clin Pharmacol*. 2003;56:588–99.
 41. Ghadiri M, Young PM, Traini D. Strategies to enhance drug absorption via nasal and pulmonary routes. *Pharmaceutics*. 2019;11:1–20.
 42. García-Fernández A, Sancenón F, Martínez-Máñez R. Mesoporous silica nanoparticles for pulmonary drug delivery. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev*. 2021;177:113953.
 43. Shu L, Wang W, Ng C, Zhang X, Huang Y, Wu C, et al. A pilot study exploiting the industrialization potential of solid lipid nanoparticle-based metered-dose inhalers. *Pharmaceutics*. 2023;15:866.
 44. Chae J, Choi Y, Tanaka M, Choi J. Inhalable nanoparticles delivery targeting alveolar macrophages for the treatment of pulmonary tuberculosis. *J Biosci Bioeng*. 2021;132:543–51.
 45. Kim J, Jozic A, Lin Y, Eygeris Y, Bloom E, Tan X, et al. Engineering lipid nanoparticles for enhanced intracellular delivery of mRNA through inhalation. *ACS Nano*. 2022;16:14792–806.
 46. Azarmi S, Roa WH, Löbenberg R. Targeted delivery of nanoparticles for the treatment of lung diseases. *Adv Drug Deliv Rev*. 2008;60:863–75.
 47. Tulbah AS. Inhaled atorvastatin nanoparticles for lung cancer. *Curr Drug Deliv*. 2022;19:1073–82.
 48. Tulbah AS, Pisano E, Scalia S, Young PM, Traini D, Ong HX. Inhaled simvastatin nanoparticles for inflammatory lung disease. *Nanomedicine*. 2017;12:2471–85.
 49. Leong EWX, Ge R. Lipid nanoparticles as delivery vehicles for inhaled therapeutics. *Biomed*. 2022;10:2179.
 50. Kumar R, Siril PF, Javid F. Unusual anti-leukemia activity of nanoformulated naproxen and other non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. *Mater Sci Eng C Mater Biol Appl*. 2016;69:1335–44.
 51. Buhecha MD, Lansley AB, Somavarapu S, Pannala AS. Development and characterization of PLA nanoparticles for

-
- pulmonary drug delivery: co-encapsulation of theophylline and budesonide, a hydrophilic and lipophilic drug. *J Drug Deliv Sci Technol.* 2019;53:101128.
52. Yuan S, Qian D, Su W. Fabrication of co-polymeric nanoformulation loaded with antibiotic ofloxacin and immunosuppressant tacrolimus for pediatric sepsis-induced acute lung injury. *Mater Express.* 2023;13:1192–202.
 53. Rashid J, Patel B, Nozik-Grayck E, McMurtry IF, Stenmark KR, Ahsan F. Inhaled sildenafil as an alternative to oral sildenafil in the treatment of pulmonary arterial hypertension (PAH). *J Control Release.* 2017;250:96–106.
 54. Li H, Yao Y, Fu H. Novel pediatric suspension of nanoparticulate zafirlukast for the treatment of asthma: assessment and evaluation in animal model. *Micro Nano Lett.* 2021;16:485–91.
 55. Lange CF, Hancock REW, Samuel J, Finlay WH. In vitro aerosol delivery and regional airway surface liquid concentration of a liposomal cationic peptide. *J Pharm Sci.* 2001;90:1647–57.
 56. Zhang H, Leal J, Soto MR, Smyth HDC, Ghosh D. Aerosolizable lipid nanoparticles for pulmonary delivery of mRNA through design of experiments. *Pharmaceutics.* 2020;12:1–16.
 57. Virginio VG, Bandeira NC, dos Leal FMA, Lancellotti M, Zaha A, Ferreira HB. Assessment of the adjuvant activity of mesoporous silica nanoparticles in recombinant *Mycoplasma hypopneumoniae* antigen vaccines. *Heliyon.* 2017;3:00225.
 58. Bogle C, Colan SD, Miyamoto SD, Choudhry S, Baez-Hernandez N, Brickler MM, et al. Treatment strategies for cardiomyopathy in children: a scientific statement from the American Heart Association. *Circulation.* 2023;148:174–95.
 59. Pasquali SK, Hall M, Slonim AD, Jenkins KJ, Marino BS, Cohen MS, et al. Off-label use of cardiovascular medications in children hospitalized with congenital and acquired heart disease. *Circ Cardiovasc Qual Outcomes.* 2008;1:74–83.
 60. Bajcetic M, Jelisavcic M, Mitrovic J, Divac N, Simeunovic S, Samardzic R, et al. Off label and unlicensed drugs use in paediatric cardiology. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol.* 2005;61:775–9.
 61. Kimland E, Nydert P, Odland V, Böttiger Y, Lindemalm S. Pediatric drug use with focus on off-label prescriptions at Swedish hospitals—a nationwide study. *Acta Paediatr Int J Paediatr.* 2012;101:772–8.
 62. Watt K, Li JS, Benjamin DK, Cohen-Wolkowicz M. Pediatric cardiovascular drug dosing in critically ill children and extra-corporeal membrane oxygenation. *J Cardiovasc Pharmacol.* 2011;58:126.
 63. El-Sayed NM, El-Bakary MA, Ibrahim MA, Elgamal MA, ElZorkany HES, Elshoky HA. Synthesis and characterization of mussel-inspired nanocomposites based on dopamine-chitosan-iron oxide for wound healing: in vitro study. *Int J Pharm.* 2023;632:122538.
 64. Kurobe H, Maxfield MW, Tara S, Rocco KA, Bagi PS, Yi T, et al. Development of small diameter nanofiber tissue engineered arterial grafts. *PLoS ONE.* 2015;10: e0120328.
 65. Li X, Zhou J, Liu Z, Chen J, Lü S, Sun H, et al. A PNIPAAm-based thermosensitive hydrogel containing SWCNTs for stem cell transplantation in myocardial repair. *Biomaterials.* 2014;35:5679–88.
 66. Zhou J, Chen J, Sun H, Qiu X, Mou Y, Liu Z, et al. Engineering the heart: evaluation of conductive nanomaterials for improving implant integration and cardiac function. *Sci Reports.* 2014;4:1–11.
 67. Sridharan D, Palaniappan A, Blackstone BN, Dougherty JA, Kumar N, Seshagiri PB, et al. In situ differentiation of human-induced pluripotent stem cells into functional cardiomyocytes on a coaxial PCL-gelatin nanofibrous scaffold. *Mater Sci Eng C.* 2021;118:111354.
 68. Sridharan D, Palaniappan A, Blackstone BN, Powell HM, Khan

-
- M. Electrospun aligned coaxial nanofibrous scaffold for cardiac repair. *Methods Mol Biol.* 2021;2193:129–40.
69. Wang L, Liu Y, Ye G, He Y, Li B, Guan Y, et al. Injectable and conductive cardiac patches repair infarcted myocardium in rats and minipigs. *Nat Biomed Eng.* 2021;5:1157–73.
70. Sun R, Wang X, Nie Y, Hu A, Liu H, Zhang K, et al. Targeted trapping of endogenous endothelial progenitor cells for myocardial ischemic injury repair through neutrophil-mediated SPIO nanoparticle-conjugated CD34 antibody delivery and imaging. *Acta Biomater.* 2022;146:421–33.
71. Zanon D, Gallelli L, Rovere F, Paparazzo R, Maximova N, Lazzerini M, et al. Off-label prescribing patterns of antiemetics in children: a multicenter study in Italy. *Eur J Pediatr.* 2013;172:361–7.
72. Karesh A, Tomaino J, Mulberg AE. Off-label use of medicine in pediatrics: Focus on gastrointestinal diseases. *Curr Opin Pediatr.* 2013;25:612–7.
73. Belayneh A, Abatneh E, Abebe D, Getachew M, Kebede B, Dessie B. Off-label medication use in pediatrics and associated factors at public hospitals in east Gojjam zone. *Ethiopia SAGE Open Med.* 2022;10:20503121221096536.
74. Zhaksylyk A, Nurbakyt A, Grjibovski A, Kaussova G, Buleshov M. Epidemiology of gastrointestinal disease among children and adolescents in Kazakhstan: 2012–2019. *Open Access Maced J Med Sci.* 2021;9:1244–9.
75. Scarpato E, Kolacek S, Jojkic-Pavkov D, Konjik V, Živković N, Roman E, et al. Prevalence of functional gastrointestinal disorders in children and adolescents in the Mediterranean Region of Europe. *Clin Gastroenterol Hepatol.* 2018;16:870–6.
76. Blanco-Llamero C, Galindo-Camacho RM, Fonseca J, Santini A, Señoráns FJ, Souto EB. Development of lipid nanoparticles containing omega-3-rich extract of microalga *nannochloropsis gaditana*. *Foods.* 2022;11:3749.
77. Xing YB, Liu X, Li X, Ding F, Zhang JY, Guo XH. PEG-PCL modification and intestinal sustained-release of solid lipid nanoparticles for improving oral bioavailability of 2-methoxyestradiol. *J Liposome Res.* 2019;29:207–14.
78. Doktorovová S, Kovacevic AB, Garcia ML, Souto EB. Preclinical safety of solid lipid nanoparticles and nanostructured lipid carriers: current evidence from in vitro and in vivo evaluation. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm.* 2016;108:235–52.
79. Permana AD, Sam A, Marzaman ANF, Rahim A, Nainu F, Bahar MA, et al. Solid lipid nanoparticles cyclodextrin-decorated incorporated into gellan gum-based dry floating in situ delivery systems for controlled release of bioactive compounds of safflower (*Carthamus tinctorius*, L.): a proof of concept study in biorelevant media. *Int J Biol Macromol.* 2023;237:124084.
80. de Castro KC, Coco JC, dos Santos ÉM, Ataíde JA, Martínez RM, do Nascimento MHM, et al. Pluronic® triblock copolymer-based nanoformulations for cancer therapy: a 10-year overview. *J Control Release.* 2023;353:802–22.
81. Zhang M, Xu C, Liu D, Han MK, Wang L, Merlina D. Oral delivery of nanoparticles loaded with ginger active compound, 6-shogaol, attenuates ulcerative colitis and promotes wound healing in a murine model of ulcerative colitis. *J Crohns Colitis.* 2018;12:217–29.
82. Ren Y, Qi C, Ruan S, Cao G, Ma Z, Zhang X. Selenized polymer-lipid hybrid nanoparticles for oral delivery of tripterine with ameliorative oral anti-enteritis activity and bioavailability. *Pharmaceutics.* 2023;15:821.
83. Diao J, Xia Y, Jiang X, Qiu J, Cheng S, Su J, et al. Silicon dioxide nanoparticles induced neurobehavioral impairments by disrupting microbiota–gut–brain axis. *J Nanobiotechnology.* 2021;19:1–20.

-
84. Gao Y, Ye Y, Wang J, Zhang H, Wu Y, Wang Y, et al. Effects of titanium dioxide nanoparticles on nutrient absorption and metabolism in rats: distinguishing the susceptibility of amino acids, metal elements, and glucose. *Nanotoxicology*. 2020;14:1301–23.
 85. Zhu X, Li H, Zhou L, Jiang H, Ji M, Chen J. Evaluation of the gut microbiome alterations in healthy rats after dietary exposure to different synthetic ZnO nanoparticles. *Life Sci*. 2023;312:121250.
 86. Muthu MS, Leong DT, Mei L, Feng SS. Nanotheranostics - application and further development of nanomedicine strategies for advanced theranostics. *Theranostics*. 2014;4:660–77.
 87. Chen WH, Xu XD, Jia HZ, Lei Q, Luo GF, Cheng SX, et al. Therapeutic nanomedicine based on dual-intelligent functionalized gold nanoparticles for cancer imaging and therapy *in vivo*. *Biomaterials*. 2013;34:8798–807.
 88. Taratula O, Schumann C, Naleway MA, Pang AJ, Chon KJ, Taratula O. A multifunctional theranostic platform based on phthalocyanine-loaded dendrimer for image-guided drug delivery and photodynamic therapy. *Mol Pharm*. 2013;10:3946–58.
 89. Chandrasekharan P, Maity D, Yong CX, Chuang KH, Ding J, Feng SS. Vitamin E (d-alpha-tocopheryl-copoly(ethylene glycol) 1000 succinate) micelles-superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles for enhanced radiotherapy and MRI. *Biomaterials*. 2011;32:5663–72.
 90. Muthu MS, Kulkarni SA, Raju A, Feng SS. Theranostic liposomes of TPGS coating for targeted co-delivery of docetaxel and quantum dots. *Biomaterials*. 2012;33:3494–501.
 91. Robinson JT, Welsher K, Tabakman SM, Sherlock SP, Wang H, Luong R, et al. High performance *in vivo* near-IR (>1 μm) imaging and photothermal cancer therapy with carbon nanotubes. *Nano Res*. 2010;3:779–93.
 92. Pan J, Liu Y, Feng SS. Multifunctional nanoparticles of biodegradable copolymer blend for cancer diagnosis and treatment. *Nanomedicine (Lond)*. 2010;5:347–60.
 93. Akpa PA, Peter IE, Onwuka AM, Obi BC, Akunne MO, Nworu CS, et al. Nanotheranostics: platforms, current applications, and mechanisms of targeting in breast and prostate cancers. *J Nanotheranostics*. 2023;4:346–83.
 94. Kim TH, Lee S, Chen X. Nanotheranostics for personalized medicine. *Expert Rev Mol Diagn*. 2013;13:257–69.
 95. Duncan R, Gaspar R. Nanomedicine (s) under the microscope. *Mol Pharm*. 2011;8:2101–41.
 96. Moon H, Kang J, Sim C, Kim J, Lee H, Chang JH, et al. Multifunctional theranostic contrast agent for photoacoustic- and ultrasound-based tumor diagnosis and ultrasound-stimulated local tumor therapy. *J Control Release*. 2015;218:63–71.
 97. Kievit FM, Zhang M. Cancer nanotheranostics: Improving imaging and therapy by targeted delivery across biological barriers. *Adv Mater*. 2011;23:217–47.
 98. Cho EC, Glaus C, Chen J, Welch MJ, Xia Y. Inorganic nanoparticle-based contrast agents for molecular imaging. *Trends Mol Med*. 2010;16:561–73.
 99. Howell M, Wang C, Mahmoud A, Hellermann G, Mohapatra SS, Mohapatra S. Dual-function theranostic nanoparticles for drug delivery and medical imaging contrast: perspectives and challenges for use in lung diseases. *Drug Deliv Transl Res*. 2013;3:352–63.
 100. Poot AJ, Lam MGEH, van Noesel MM. The current status and future potential of theranostics to diagnose and treat childhood cancer. *Front Oncol*. 2020;10:1–8.
 101. Plasschaert S, Tolboom N, Kester L, Tops B, Hoving E, Poot A, et al. IMG-04. Potential targets for theranostics in

-
- pediatric high-grade central nervous system (CNS) tumors. *Neuro Oncol.* 2023;25:47.
102. Niessen VJA, Wenker STM, Lam MGEH, van Noesel MM, Poot AJ. Biologicals as theranostic vehicles in paediatric oncology. *Nucl Med Biol.* 2022;114–115:58–64.
 103. Luo MX, Hua S, Shang QY. Application of nanotechnology in drug delivery systems for respiratory diseases (Review). *Mol Med Rep.* 2021;23:325.
 104. Zhang L, Chan JM, Gu FX, Rhee JW, Wang AZ, Radovic-Moreno AF, et al. Self-assembled lipid-polymer hybrid nanoparticles: a robust drug delivery platform. *ACS Nano.* 2008;2:1696–702.
 105. Wang J, Byrne JD, Napier ME, Desimone JM. More effective nanomedicines through particle design. *Small.* 2011;7:1919–31.
 106. Semmler-Behnke M, Kreyling WG, Lipka J, Fertsch S, Wenk A, Takenaka S, et al. Biodistribution of 1.4- and 18-nm gold particles in rats. *Small.* 2008;4:2108–11.
 107. Li W, Brown PK, Wang LV, Xia Y. Gold nanocages as contrast agents for photoacoustic imaging. *Contrast Media Mol Imaging.* 2011;6:370–7.
 108. Wang C, Wang Y, Zhang L, Miron RJ, Liang J, Shi M, et al. Pretreated macrophage-membrane-coated gold nanocages for precise drug delivery for treatment of bacterial infections. *Adv Mater.* 2018;30:1–8.
 109. Wang H, Wu L, Sun X. Intratracheal delivery of nano- and microparticles and hyperpolarized gases: a promising strategy for the imaging and treatment of respiratory disease. *Chest.* 2020;157:1579–90.
 110. Suer H, Bayram H. Liposomes as potential nanocarriers for theranostic applications in chronic inflammatory lung diseases. *Biomed Biotechnol Res J.* 2017;1:1–8.
 111. Jani V, Shivaram P, Porter TR, Kutty S. Ultrasound theranostics in adult and pediatric cardiovascular research. *Cardiovasc Drugs Ther.* 2021;35:185–90.
 112. Kutty S, Xie F, Gao S, Drvol LK, Lof J, Fletcher SE, et al. Sono-thrombolysis of intra-catheter aged venous thrombi using micro-bubble enhancement and guided three-dimensional ultrasound pulses. *J Am Soc Echocardiogr.* 2010;23:1001–6.
 113. Spivak MY, Bubnov RV, Yemets IM, Lazarenko LM, Tymoshok NO, Ulberg ZR. Development and testing of gold nanoparticles for drug delivery and treatment of heart failure: a theranostic potential for PPP cardiology. *EPMA J.* 2013;4:1–23.
 114. Zhan P, Yu B, Ouyang L. Drug repurposing: an effective strategy to accelerate contemporary drug discovery. *Drug Discov Today.* 2022;27:1785–8.
 115. Ashburn TT, Thor KB. Drug repositioning: identifying and developing new uses for existing drugs. *Nat Rev Drug Discov.* 2004;3:673–83.
 116. Pushpakom S, Iorio F, Eyers PA, Escott KJ, Hopper S, Wells A, et al. Drug repurposing: progress, challenges and recommendations. *Nat Rev Drug Discov.* 2018;18:41–58.
 117. Nosengo N. Can you teach old drugs new tricks? *Nature.* 2016;534:314–6.
 118. Scannell JW, Blanckley A, Boldon H, Warrington B. Diagnosing the decline in pharmaceutical R&D efficiency. *Nat Rev Drug Discov.* 2012;11:191–200.
 119. Krishnamurthy N, Grimshaw AA, Axson SA, Choe SH, Miller JE. Drug repurposing: a systematic review on root causes, barriers and facilitators. *BMC Health Serv Res.* 2022;22:1–17.
 120. Verbaanderd C, Rooman I, Huys I. Exploring new uses for existing drugs: innovative mechanisms to fund independent

clinical research. *Trials*. 2021;22:1–13.

121. Albuquerque PC, Zicker F, Fonseca BP. Advancing drug repurposing research: trends, collaborative networks, innovation and knowledge leaders. *Drug Discov Today*. 2022;27:103396.
122. Schubert M, Hansen S, Leefmann J, Guan K. Repurposing antidiabetic drugs for cardiovascular disease. *Front Physiol*. 2020;11:568632.
123. Tejera E, Pérez-Castillo Y, Chamorro A, Cabrera-Andrade A, Sanchez ME. A multi-objective approach for drug repurposing in preeclampsia. *Molecules*. 2021;26:1–19.
124. Fernández Álvaro E, Voong Vinh P, de Cozar C, Willé DR, Urones B, Cortés A, et al. The repurposing of Tebipenem piv-oxil as alternative therapy for severe gastrointestinal infections caused by extensively drug-resistant *Shigella* spp (eLife (2022) 11 PII: e83117). *Elife*. 2022;11:e69798.
125. Ezat AA, Abduljalil JM, Elghareib AM, Samir A, Elfiky AA. The discovery of novel antivirals for the treatment of mpox: is drug repurposing the answer? *Expert Opin Drug Discov*. 2023;18:551–61.
126. Yan R, He J, Liu G, Zhong J, Xu J, Zheng K, et al. Drug repositioning for hand, foot, and mouth disease. *Viruses*. 2022;15:75.
127. Reddy DS, Sinha A, Kumar A, Saini VK. Drug re-engineering and repurposing: a significant and rapid approach to tuberculosis drug discovery. *Arch Pharm (Weinheim)*. 2022;355:e2200214.
128. Gottlieb A, Stein GY, Ruppin E, Sharan R. PREDICT: a method for inferring novel drug indications with application to personalized medicine. *Mol Syst Biol*. 2011;7:1–9.
129. Park K. A review of computational drug repurposing. *Transl Clin Pharmacol*. 2019;27:59–63.
130. Anusuya S, Keshewani M, Priya KV, Vimala A, Shanmugam G, Velmurugan D, et al. Drug-target interactions: prediction methods and applications. *Curr Protein Pept Sci*. 2018;19:537–61.
131. Sachdev K, Gupta MK. A comprehensive review of feature based methods for drug target interaction prediction. *J Biomed Inform*. 2019;93:103159.
132. Wang L, You ZH, Chen X, Xia SX, Liu F, Yan X, et al. A computational-based method for predicting drug-target interactions by using stacked autoencoder deep neural network. *J Comput Biol*. 2018;25:361–73.
133. Beck BR, Shin B, Choi Y, Park S, Kang K. Predicting commercially available antiviral drugs that may act on the novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) through a drug-target interaction deep learning model. *Comput Struct Biotechnol J*. 2020;18:784–90.
134. Nguyen T, Le H, Quinn TP, Nguyen T, Le TD, Venkatesh S. GraphDTA: predicting drug target binding affinity with graph neural networks. *Bioinformatics*. 2021;37:1140–7.
135. Shin B, Park S, Kang K, Ho JC. Self-attention based molecule representation for predicting drug-target interaction. *Proc Mach Learn Res*. 2019;106:1–18.
136. Wu Z, Li W, Liu G, Tang Y. Network-based methods for prediction of drug-target interactions. *Front Pharmacol*. 2018;9:1–14.
137. Ton AT, Gentile F, Hsing M, Ban F, Cherkasov A. Rapid identification of potential inhibitors of SARS-CoV-2 main protease by deep docking of 1.3 billion compounds. *Mol Inform*. 2020;39:1–7.
138. Pliakos K, Vens C. Drug-target interaction prediction with tree-ensemble learning and output space reconstruction. *BMC Bioinformatics*. 2020;21:1V.
139. Öztürk H, Özgür A, Ozkirimli E. DeepDTA: deep drug-target binding affinity prediction. *Bioinformatics*.

2018;34:i821–9.

140. Feng Q, Dueva E, Cherkasov A, Ester M. PADME: a deep learning-based framework for drug-target interaction prediction. 2018;arXiv:1807.
141. Zheng Y, Wu Z. A machine learning-based biological drug-target interaction prediction method for a tripartite heterogeneous net-work. *ACS Omega*. 2021;6:3037–45.
142. Wang S, Guo Y, Wang Y, Sun H, Huang J. 2019 Smiles-Bert: large scale unsupervised pre-training for molecular property pre-diction. *Proceedings of the 10th ACM international conference on bioinformatics, computational biology and health informatics (BCB '19)*. New York, USA: Association for Computing Machinery; 2019.
143. Mikolov T, Chen K, Corrado G, Dean J. Efficient estimation of word representations in vector space. *1st Int conf learn repre-sent ICLR 2013—Work Track Proc. International conference on learning representations*; 2013.
144. Du J, Jia P, Dai Y, Tao C, Zhao Z, Zhi D. Gene2vec: distributed representation of genes based on co-expression. *BMC Genomics*. 2019;20:82.
145. Hochreiter S, Schmidhuber J. Long short-term memory. *Neural Comput*. 1997;9:1735–80.
146. Guo Z, Yu W, Zhang C, Jiang M, Chawla N V. GraSeq: graph and sequence fusion learning for molecular property prediction. *Proceedings of the 29th ACM International Conference on Information & Knowledge Management*; 2020.
147. Öztürk H, Ozkirimli E, Özgür A. WideDTA: prediction of drug-target binding affinity. 2019. Available from: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1902.04166>. Accessed 8 July 2024.
148. De SJG, Fernandes MAC. A novel deep neural network technique for drug—target interaction. *Pharmaceutics*. 2021;14:625.
149. Kwon S, Yoon S. DeepCCI: end-to-end deep learning for chemical-chemical interaction prediction. *Proceedings of the 8th ACM international conference on bioinformatics, computational biology, and health informatics*; 2017.
150. Li J, Pu Y, Tang J, Zou Q, Guo F. DeepAVP: a dual-channel deep neural network for identifying variable-length antiviral peptides. *IEEE J Biomed Heal Informatics*. 2020;24:3012–9.
151. Bung N, Krishnan SR, Bulusu G, Roy A. De novo design of new chemical entities for SARS-CoV-2 using artificial intelligence. *Future Med Chem*. 2021;13:575–85.
152. Guney E, Menche J, Vidal M, Barábasi AL. Network-based in silico drug efficacy screening. *Nat Commun*. 2016;7:10331.
153. Alaimo S, Giugno R, Pulvirenti A. Recommendation techniques for drug–target interaction prediction and drug repositioning. In: Carugo O, Eisenhaber F, editors. *Methods in molecular biology*. 2nd ed. Hertfordshire: Human Press; 2016. p. 441–62.
154. Mei JP, Kwok CK, Yang P, Li XL, Zheng J. Drug-target interaction prediction by learning from local information and neighbors. *Bioinformatics*. 2013;29:238–45.
155. Khatri P, Roedder S, Kimura N, De Vusser K, Morgan AA, Gong Y, et al. A common rejection module (CRM) for acute rejection across multiple organs identifies novel therapeutics for organ transplantation. *J Exp Med*. 2013;210:2205–21.
156. Eisenstein M. Big data: the power of petabytes. *Nature*. 2015;527:S2–4.